

Seagrass Bioregional Species Key:

1 Temperate North Atlantic Bioregion

Species identification key including photo guide, global range maps, drawings, and flowers.

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With ratings from:
IUCN Red List of Threatened Species
Seagrass Red List

*Bioregional Guide to the Seagrass Species of the World. 2025. F.T. Short.
Available on-line www.SeagrassNet.org.*

Zm *Zostera marina*

Bioregion
1

Key

- Flat leaves to 3 m with closed sheath
- Leaf tip smoothly rounded
- Rhizome robust with terminal shoots
- 2 bundles of roots per node
- Monoecious

Flowering Parts

female & male

female

seedling

seed

Extinction Risk: Least Concern

Hw *Halodule wrightii*

Extinction Risk: Least Concern

Key

- Leaves flat and thin
- Leaf tip usually 2 points
- Leaves 2-22 cm long
- Rhizome whitish
- Dioecious
- Depth -1 to 20 m
- Sometimes leaves red or black

Flowering Parts

Rm *Ruppia maritima*

Bioregion
1

Key

- Leaves flat and thin
- Leaf tapers to tip to point
- Leaves 4-22 cm long
- Depth -1 to 20 m

Flowering Parts

Extinction Risk: Least Concern

Rc *Ruppia cirrhosa*

Extinction Risk: Least Concern

Bioregion

1

Key

- Leaves flat and thin
- Leaf tapers to tip, 25 cm long
- Fruits cluster on spiral stem
- Depth intertidal to 20 m

Flowering Parts

Zn *Nanozostera noltii*

Bioregion
1

Extinction Risk: Least Concern

Found in the
Eastern Atlantic

Key

- Flat narrow leaves to 30 cm with open sheath
- Leaf tip rounded and unevenly notched
- Thin rhizome, shoots at each node
- Flowers on branched stem
- Monoecious

Flowering Parts

Stage

Description

- | | |
|-----|---|
| I | Yellow-green spathe, sheath closed; pistils and stamens are visible, aligned onto the stem |
| II | Pistils (IIa) and/or stamens erect (IIb); styles and stigma and/or anthers are outside the sheath |
| III | Stigma brown, start to depart from spathe; often with stamens already detached from the spathe |
| IV | Green spathe with immature seeds; sheath closed |
| V | Green/brown spathe, dark brown seeds are visible, sheath open |

Ankel et al 2021

Cn *Cymodocea nodosa*

Bioregion
1

Key

- Flat leaves to 30 cm
- Leaf tip rounded, slightly serrated
- Rhizome robust with one root per node
- Flowers emerge from sheath
- Dioecious

Flowering
Parts

fruit

male

Extinction Risk: Least Concern

Found in the
Eastern Atlantic

Global Seagrass Species References

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